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Anwaril Hamidy
 UIN Sultan Aji Muhammad Idris Samarinda
 Phone +6281347076592
anwarilhamidyaiainsmd@gmail.com

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Our decision is to: Accept Submission

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 AHMAD JUHAIDI <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>
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